
ASSESSMENT SYSTEM BASED ON INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES METHODS OF INCREASING EFFICIENCY

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innovative education,
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ABSTRACT

This article examines the students' knowledge in an international manner theoretical basis and content of using assessment systems, assessment analysis of systems methodology, international assessment systems Analytical information about specific features of use given. Also, monitor students' knowledge of computer science practical use of international assessment systems basics, a general description of the use of international assessment systems, integrated to monitor student learning.

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Innovative education in improving the efficiency of computer science lessons innovative use of technologies for teacher training approach, perfect mastery of its methods is important. In this case, it is necessary to organize science classes step by step appropriate. In the first step, basic information about the science is provided.

In the second stage, usually the most relevant, controversial of the demands of the period issues are discussed. Search, think, create, work will be done. In the third step, theoretical rules are put forward in depth level is stated. It is known that independent creative thinking is in the study environment it is formed and developed in the process of overcoming emerging difficulties. In the fourth stage, feedback, material for communication is given. In the fifth stage, the subjects learned by the teacher are correct their understanding is controlled, for self-control in them different forms of assignments (oral question-and-answer, written and test). are used and the correct answers are given. Tasks are verbs that express specific actions of teachers needs to be expressed. In accordance with the levels of thinking of mastering special attention should be paid to the use of more verbs. Because, they ensure that the material is mastered at high intellectual levels. Each assignment only covers one concept or rule should be checked and explained in a concise, understandable manner. Assignments are structured in oral question-answer, written and test forms

possible It is also effective to create tasks of different forms for the same purpose will be. Because in this, bachelor teachers have a specific task an opportunity is created to objectively assess their knowledge. question-and-answer, pedagogue directly with bachelor and master teachers interview, in which the answers to the questions are evaluated. Compose written tasks, from the option of key words and phrases implies use. It is interactive in creating assignments in this form paying attention to the number of tasks solved using methods must Because, cluster, cinquefoil, Venn diagram, insert, conceptual table, Interactive methods such as case study, T-schema creation, technical dictation writing application develops the thinking ability of bachelor and master teachers, ensures learning material at high intellectual levels. We will consider some of these methods in the following topics. Among the above mentioned and other interactive methods in the educational process The use of creative activities of undergraduate teachers, moreover, this requires mastery of the work at the levels of Bloom's taxonomy. Improper use of interactive methods reduces the effectiveness of these methods or cause a misconception about it. Creating independent thinking without building self-confidence not allowed. At the same time, self-confidence means independent thinking requires. Every undergraduate teacher is confident in the importance of his opinion the generator must act to obtain information. Otherwise, he is sluggish in training and cannot think independently. Bloom's Taxonomy is a theme for test makers to determine which category of educational goals the materials correspond to also provides comfort. Learning identified as a result of its application at the levels where it is impossible to determine the goals, in relation to them it is possible to express it in a generalized form and create test tasks. Or, first, learning objectives in a more general form

by taxonomy category defined and then consistent with them and more clearly expressing the final result a verb can be selected and then test tasks can be created. When creating test assignments it is also necessary to pay attention to the fact that the number of tests at the reproductive level of mastering does not increase. Material at creative levels determining mastery - open, closed with several correct answers, it is important to use forms of testing such as eligibility criteria. To them let's stop. Open tests. If the text of the test task contains its base words or sentences if it is omitted, such a task is called an open (unfinished) test is called In the tests of this form, the bachelor's teachers have one or two words It is assumed that they will give short and clear answers. Appendices to the test about it must be stated in the referral. For the answer in the empty space of the blank the necessary space is left. Closed tests. Such tests consist of questions and multiple answers, one of these answers will be correct, the rest will be similar to correct, but incorrect. The number of suggested answers should be from two to five or more possible For example: How do we know if a file has a virus?

- a) unfamiliar signs appear.
- b) unknown.

Compliance tests. The essence of these tests is many based on the need to determine the compatibility of elements with others. This tasks is a two-word construction "to determine compatibility". should be based on, for example: Check the compliance of the devices of the "computer" with the following,

1. basic
 2. addition
- a) System board,
 - b) mouse,
 - c) column,
 - d) printer,
 - e) scanner,
 - f) keyboard,
 - g) monitor,
 - h) plotter.

In this principle of pedagogical technology, teachers are given individual attention will be allowed to master. Innovative in improving the efficiency of computer science lessons follow the following rules for using educational Technologies it's best to:

- * to express one's opinion quickly after observation;
- * express your impressions briefly, clearly and without deviating from the topic to speak;
- * feel good in the most intense conversations;
- * start and end the conversation positively;
- * try to understand the interlocutor during the conversation;
- * be ready to hear criticism, etc.

At the same time, it is intended to achieve the following results: distinguish between traditional and non-traditional educational process, analysis, generalization, conclusion and their main to tell the shortcomings;

- * an approach to teaching based on innovative educational technologies and justify the methods;

- * introducing innovations into the educational process, innovative education in it technologies, use of interactive methods and lessons understand the need to introduce them to their training;

- * new, modern innovative methods and scientifically based formation of the educational process based on principles and laws;

- * designing the educational process, goals and tasks clarification, in which the use of Bloom's categories, electronic, teaching based on multimedia systems;

- * accurate and accurate knowledge based on fast and non-traditional methods assessment;

- * Analytical approach to the topic chosen from the taught subject write an abstract based on; Innovative teaching in his subject training in a technology-based approach designing methodological development;

- * innovative education in conducting an open class and teaching in it approach based on technologies and method, form, methods show usage.

The content, forms, methods and tools of the educational goal are in pedagogy traditional categories used to analyze educational processes is considered These are the categories of a certain subject, specialty or a pedagogue who organizes the educational process by specialty emerges as the subject of his activity. Noted pedagogy Pedagogical and educational that guides the categories in accordance with the purpose the legality and criteria of its activity act as a systematizing factor. For many years, the size of the pedagogical categories shown is society has been sufficient to realize its goals at the level of demand. Tan It should be noted that the masses of pedagogues are aware of the current pedagogical situation those who have been assessed as being in an unsatisfactory condition. This is pedagogical the uncertainty of the definitions and descriptions of the concepts and educational processes lack of some descriptive categories, educational purpose, content, form, lack of coherence between method and teaching tools The concept of "methodology", which is always brought under criticism, is high is characterized by having a level of subjectivity. Thoughts expressed reveals two problems in our view; First, a bachelor's and master's degree with professional pedagogical education the level of professional competence of teachers; secondly, not having special pedagogical training is professional skill, low level of literacy. Innovative educational technologies are complex integrative systems, acquisition of professional skills, competences and personal qualities by learners, aimed at mastering knowledge includes an ordered set of operations and actions. Here is the definition of educational goals (to whom and why?), introduction to the selection and development of content (what?), educational processes organization (how?), defining

educational methods and tools (what with the help of?), as well as the level of qualification of pedagogues (who?), achieved it is necessary to be based on the method of evaluating the results (how?) and others. The collective application of the mentioned criteria is the essence of the educational process and defines its technology. Designing teaching technology as a pedagogical task and we will consider it based on its solution. The determination of the pedagogical task is explained by the following: Analysis of educational goals, based on this, the content of the educational subject determination; Development of the content structure of the educational subject and its study representation in the form of a system of elements; Determining the levels of mastery of educational elements; Determining the initial level of education of undergraduate teachers educational material on which the content of the indicator educational subject is based depends on the level of mastery; It is applied to educational material base and organizational forms of education setting boundaries. Teaching technology that ensures the solution of pedagogical tasks Pedagogical activities aimed at designing methods, forms and tools of education determined by formation. In other words, the activity of a pedagogue characterized by three main constituent types: management type, information type of exchange process, types of means of information transfer and knowledge management of activities. approach to the teaching process from the point of view of activity based on the concept, its organization can be built on the basis of the following logical sequence. First, a description of the content of the educational material, it learning goals (levels of mastery), as well as the conditions of setting the pedagogical task are analyzed. Then, the training is appropriate methods and cognitive activities of future bachelor teachers control scheme is determined. Here is a list of teaching aids is made. A system of educational methods and tools created by this method combined with organizational forms, that is, technology is developed. Teaching technology is a systematic category of scientific teaching didactic application, innovative empiric of undergraduate teachers organization and analysis of the educational system based on scientific approaches aimed at establishing and achieving high results in their development is a process. This view of education consists of the following main parts: the purpose of education; content of education; motivation of teaching and tools; organizing the teaching process; undergraduate teachers; pedagogue; activity result. Educational technology includes two interrelated processes takes:

- Organization of the activity of the person to be trained;
- Organization of control over activity.

Modern electronic tools in the study of educational technology you can't stop. They are strategic elements of educational innovation can be called The interdisciplinary model of teaching in general education is characteristic sciences have more information than necessary. This is how the innovative teaching strategy organizes the educational process aims to achieve, in which, as before, the pedagogue is the leading element, only his attitude towards undergraduate teachers and himself will change. That's it along with this, their approach will also change. Applying modern innovative technologies to the educational

process many factors have a negative effect, including: insufficient level of provision of computers and electronic tools of educational institutions; they are the internet and not connected to other information networks; of scientific and methodical sources inadequacy (electronic manuals, laboratory works, tests are sufficientnot); on modern computer technology of pedagogues lack of skills; students have enough computers inability to use, do not know how to work with e-books; education lack of serious attention of the management of the institutions to this field of education and etc.

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